

DIRECTIONS D2.3:

Report with recommendations and guidelines on the control and operation of multi-vendor interoperable electrical energy hubs

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Executive Summary

This report constitutes the third deliverable of the DIRECTIONS project for Work Package 2 (WP2), specifically addressing Task 2.2 “Interaction characterization and stability under the influence of grid-forming converters”, Task 2.3 “Topological design and impacts on dynamics and control”, and Task 2.4 “Performance assessment and benchmarking”.

This deliverable brings together the analytical foundations, methodological developments, and validation results required to formulate recommendations for the control and operation of multi-vendor interoperable energy hubs. As energy systems transition toward converter-dominated systems and increasingly complex AC/DC infrastructures, the interplay between converter behavior, network design, and operational strategies becomes essential to ensuring stability, scalability, and interoperability.

Figure 1: Overview of the DIRECTIONS control approach, with the elements addressed in this deliverable highlighted.

The overall DIRECTIONS approach is illustrated in Fig. 1, which is organized along three axes: the methods and tools used to model and analyze converter-rich AC/DC systems, the analysis of converter behavior at both

device level and system level, and the application to relevant case studies. The first axis was the main focus of the previous deliverable D2.2. Building on those foundations, the present deliverable concentrates on the central axis. Within this central axis, the work follows two complementary tracks: small-signal analysis, which uses analytical and frequency-domain methods to characterize interaction mechanisms and extract structural insight into stability, and large-signal analysis, which uses time-domain EMT simulations and controller-hardware-in-the-loop experiments to assess transient behavior and coordinated operation.

These interaction studies yield a systematic classification of the dominant mechanisms, an analysis of their root causes, and corresponding mitigation strategies, with particular emphasis on control design and on multi-vendor converter interoperability. The deliverable also addresses the role of HVDC topology, including bipolar versus parallel-monopolar configurations and multi-terminal arrangements, and shows how these choices govern both small-signal interaction patterns and large-signal coordinated operation.

Overall, this deliverable provides actionable insights into how multi-vendor energy hubs can be designed and operated to ensure stable, flexible, and scalable performance. The combined outcomes of interaction analysis, control and topology design, and performance assessment form a coherent set of guidelines that support the development of future converter-rich energy systems aligned with the objectives of the DIRECTIONS project.

List of Abbreviations

Notation	Description
AC	Alternating Current
AHS	Active Harmonic Suppression
C-HiL	Controller Hardware-in-the-Loop
DC	Direct Current
DUT	Device Under Test
EMT	Electromagnetic Transient
EMTDC	Electromagnetic Transient including DC
FD-JB	Frequency-Dependent Power Flow Jacobian
TVR	Transient Virtual Resistance
GFL	Grid Following
GFM	Grid Forming
GNC	Generalized Nyquist Criterion
HVDC	High Voltage Direct Current
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
LTI	Linear Time Invariant
MMC	Modular Multilevel Converter
MTDC	Multi Terminal DC
MOR	Model Order Reduction
PE	Power Electronics
ROCOF	Rate of Change of Frequency
ROM	Reduced Order Model
SCR	Short Circuit Ratio
VFF	Voltage Feedforward
VI	Virtual Impedance
VSC	Voltage Source Converter
VSM	Virtual Synchronous Machine
WT	Wind Turbine

Chapter 1

Small-Signal Analysis

This chapter summarizes the research contributions developed within WP2 that address small-signal stability analysis in converter-dominated power systems. The presented works span both the device level and the system level, reflecting the broad range of stability challenges introduced by the increasing deployment of power-electronic converters and GFM technologies. The objective of this chapter is not to develop a single unified methodology, but rather to provide an overview of several complementary studies that investigate different aspects of converter-driven stability phenomena. Although the individual sections address distinct research questions, they are connected by the common goal of understanding, characterizing, and assessing dynamic interactions in modern power systems through small-signal analysis techniques.

1.1 Impact of GFM wind turbine on inter-area oscillation and its model order reduction

As stability challenges intensify in converter-dominated systems, grid forming (GFM) has emerged as a key enabler for sustaining system performance. However, GFM converters are not only a source of support. Instead, they can also introduce new risks, as their dynamics may interact with the classical electromechanical modes of the interconnected AC network.

Our work in [1] investigates how the modeling fidelity of GFM wind turbines (GFM-WTs) affects the study of inter-area oscillations¹. The motivation is that GFM control, designed to emulate synchronous generator (SG) dynamics, introduces low-frequency drive-train modes that can in-

¹This section summarizes the work published in: D. Lee, F. J. Cifuentes Garcia, and J. Beerten, "Impact of grid-forming wind turbine model order reduction on interaction studies with inter-area oscillations," *Sustainable Energy, Grids and Networks*, 2025 [1].

Figure 1.1: Time-domain simulation results of inter-area oscillation triggered by GFM parameter [1].

teract with traditional inter-area modes in mixed SG/converter systems. A detailed 19th-order state-space model of a type-4 GFM-WT is first constructed and validated against nonlinear electromagnetic transient (EMT) frequency scans. The admittance reveals a characteristic drive-train oscillatory peak around 2.1 Hz that is absent in grid-following (GFL) counterparts. Two reduced-order models (ROMs) (16th and 14th order) are then derived by progressively simplifying the rotor-side and grid-side current-control dynamics. Their validity is assessed through a novel internal-structure analysis of the state matrix, which visualizes the coupling paths between subsystems and reveals that the DC voltage state is the sole interaction channel between the rotor-side converter and grid-side converter. Moreover, the impact of model order reduction (MOR) is examined by eigenvalue comparison, observability analysis, and frequency response matching. This reduced-order modeling is applied to a modified two-area system in which one SG per

area is replaced by a GFM-WT, eigenvalue-trajectory sweeps and parametric frequency-response studies show that virtual synchronous machine (VSM) damping and droop significantly improve inter-area mode stability, that higher virtual inertia increases synchronizing power but requires careful tuning, and that low drive-train damping can excite an internal WT instability even when the inter-area mode itself remains stable. All findings are validated through PSCAD/EMTDC simulations, confirming both the computational efficiency of the ROMs and the critical influence of GFM-WT control and mechanical parameters on system-wide oscillatory stability. Fig. 1.1 shows the inter-area oscillation instability induced by the interactions between synchronous generators and GFM-WTs.

1.2 Impact of AC/DC coupling dynamics on stability studies

Because the converter dynamically links the AC and DC sides, stability conclusions drawn from one port alone may shift once the cross-port coupling is accounted for. Whether this coupling is modeled explicitly therefore affects which interactions the analysis can capture².

Our work in [2] investigates how AC/DC coupling dynamics influence control interactions and stability assessment in converter-dominated systems. To demonstrate how simplified approaches considering only the AC side can mislead the stability conclusions, the work adopts an admittance-based framework that captures the full 3×3 AC/DC admittance of the device under test (DUT), a modular multilevel converter (MMC) operated in GFL mode with DC-voltage droop control, including the cross-coupling terms between AC and DC ports. The expression of this admittance with proper per-unitization can be expressed as

$$\mathbf{i}(j\omega) = \mathbf{Y}(j\omega)\mathbf{v}(j\omega) \quad (1.1)$$

$$\mathbf{Y}(j\omega) = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{Y}_{ac}(j\omega) & \mathbf{Y}_{acdc}(j\omega) \\ \mathbf{Y}_{dcac}(j\omega) & Y_{dc}(j\omega) \end{bmatrix} \quad (1.2)$$

where $\mathbf{i}(j\omega) = [i_d(j\omega), i_q(j\omega), i_{dc}(j\omega)]^T$, $\mathbf{v}(j\omega) = [v_d(j\omega), v_q(j\omega), v_{dc}(j\omega)]^T$ denote the current and voltage vectors composed of dq -axis AC-side components and DC-side components. $\mathbf{Y}(j\omega) \in \mathbb{C}^{3 \times 3}$ is the AC/DC admittance, where $\mathbf{Y}_{ac}(j\omega) = \begin{bmatrix} Y_{dd} & Y_{dq} \\ Y_{qd} & Y_{qq} \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{C}^{2 \times 2}$ is the AC-side dq -axis admittance,

²This section summarizes the work published in: D. Lee, E. Avdiaj, F. J. Cifuentes Garcia, and J. Beerten, "Impacts of AC/DC coupling on control interaction assessment in power systems with black-box models," Cigre Paris Session, 2026 [2].

Figure 1.2: EMT time-domain simulation results with high impedance of interconnected DC-side Thevenin equivalent circuit. At 1 s, 2 s, and 3 s, the AC-side interconnected Thevenin equivalent impedance is increased gradually [2].

$Y_{dc}(j\omega) \in \mathbb{C}^{1 \times 1}$ is the DC-side admittance, and $\mathbf{Y}_{acdc} = \begin{bmatrix} Y_{ddc} \\ Y_{qdc} \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{C}^{2 \times 1}$ and $\mathbf{Y}_{dcac} = [Y_{dcd} \ Y_{dcq}] \in \mathbb{C}^{1 \times 2}$ represent the coupling admittance between AC and DC.

A key finding is that varying the DC-voltage droop gain leaves \mathbf{Y}_{ac} essentially unchanged, while substantially modifying the AC/DC coupling terms and the DC-side admittance. As a result, an AC-side only passivity assessment yields identical passivity indices across all droop settings, whereas the passivity index computed on the full coupled admittance \mathbf{Y} varies significantly around the AC weak-grid instability mode at approximately 20 Hz.

EMT time-domain simulations in Fig. 1.2 confirm the finding that the stability conclusion can be different depending on the coupling admittance. The studied system considers the interconnected AC- and DC-side systems as its RL Thevenin equivalent circuits. Although the AC-side impedance of the DUT does not change with droop gain, its stability results differ with respect to the AC-side Thevenin-equivalent impedance. This effect is invisible when the DC side is assumed ideal. Generalized Nyquist analysis further shows that only loop-gain formulations accounting for AC/DC coupling correctly predict this instability, while the AC-only loop gain fails to encircle the critical point and misses the instability entirely. Taken together, these results show that AC-side analysis alone is insufficient for accurate stability assessment in AC/DC hybrid systems. Passivity-based design methodologies widely used to guide converter integration into weak grids must therefore explicitly account for AC/DC coupling pathways to avoid steering the design in an inappropriate direction.

Figure 1.3: Bipolar HVDC links with GFM-MMCs connected to grid A [3].

1.3 Interactions between bipolar HVDC connections in GFM mode

The increasing deployment of bipolar HVDC links and the anticipated shift toward GFM control strategies introduce new stability challenges, particularly sub-synchronous interactions between converters in low-inertia power systems³. While prior studies have examined such interactions within a single bipolar link, how nearby bipolar HVDC connections equipped with GFM-MMCs influence each other when connected to a common AC system has received limited attention. Our work in [3] addresses this gap by modeling the system in Fig. 1.3 using a state-space representation and performing an eigenvalue-based small-signal stability analysis to identify and characterize dominant sub-synchronous interaction modes. The locations of the dominant eigenvalues in the complex plane are shown in Fig. 1.4a, while Fig. 1.4b presents the corresponding participation factors, highlighting the involvement of individual system components and revealing interaction patterns among the converter stations.

Participation factor and mode-shape analyses are systematically applied to understand the type of interaction each mode represents. Specifically, the mode shapes associated with eigenvalues $\lambda_{1,2}$ (Fig. 1.5) show the two GFM-MMCs at converter station 1 oscillating against each other, whereas mode $\lambda_{3,4}$ (Fig. 1.5) captures a similar internal oscillatory behavior at converter station 3. Therefore, mode $\lambda_{1,2}$ and $\lambda_{3,4}$ depict intra-station interac-

³This section summarizes the work published in: F. G. Puricelli and J. Beerten, "Evaluation of interactions between bipolar HVDC connections with grid-forming converters," *22nd IET International Conference on AC and DC Power Transmission (ACDC Global 2025)*, pp. 85-90, 2025 [3].

Figure 1.4: Dominant sub-synchronous modes between nearby bipolar HVDC systems with MMCs in GFM mode [3].

tions between the GFM-MMCs at station 1 and station 2, respectively. Modes $\lambda_{5,6}$ and $\lambda_{7,8}$ instead indicate inter-station interactions between stations 1 and 2. Mode $\lambda_{5,6}$ (Fig. 1.5) represents an anti-phase interaction between the two converter stations operating in GFM mode, while an in-phase dynamic response of both stations is observed for eigenvalues $\lambda_{7,8}$, as illustrated by the mode shape in Fig. 1.5. Furthermore, the study highlights the influence of electrical distance, GFM control parameter tuning, and power-flow operating conditions on the observed interactions. The results presented in [3] demonstrate that sub-synchronous interactions can arise not only within a single HVDC link but also between separate links connected to the same AC system. The strength and nature of these interactions depend on factors such as overhead-line length, mismatches in virtual inertia or control bandwidths, and relative power transfer levels. In particular, converter stations with similar control dynamics or comparable power-flow conditions tend to exhibit stronger coupling. Overall, the work provides both a structured analytical methodology and key practical insights for identifying, interpreting, and mitigating stability risks associated with multiple GFM-controlled bipolar HVDC systems connected to a common AC grid.

1.4 High-frequency interactions with MMCs in HVDC systems

Beyond the low-frequency and sub-synchronous interactions discussed so far, HVDC systems can also exhibit stability risks at kHz frequencies⁴.

Our work in [4], the impact of detailed high-frequency transformer

⁴This section summarizes the work published in: J. Kircheis and J. Beerten, “High-Frequency Interactions with MMCs in HVDC Systems: Impact of Transformer Parasitics and Frequency Dependence,” in 2025 57th North American Power Symposium (NAPS), 2025, pp. 1–6 [4].

Figure 1.5: Visual representation of the oscillations represented by each of the dominant sub-synchronous interaction modes[3].

modeling on the stability of MMC-based HVDC systems in the kHz range is examined, focusing on how enhanced transformer modeling affects small-signal behavior. The work focuses on evaluating how enhanced transformer modeling affects small-signal behavior in the kHz range. To this end, the authors propose a grey-box transformer model that incorporates stray capacitances and frequency-dependent winding resistance derived from measured harmonic loss factors, and integrate this model into an MMC frequency-domain framework based on admittance and passivity analysis. The results show that the detailed transformer representation significantly alters high-frequency interaction characteristics: it improves damping and passivity up to approximately 7 kHz compared to the RL model, increases phase margins near 3 kHz, but introduces new non-dissipative regions and reduced margins around 7–9 kHz due to transformer-induced resonances. The impact of the assessed transformer modeling on the passivity properties of an HVDC-MMC is depicted in Fig. 1.6, where λ_{\min} denotes the passivity of the system. A system is passive when $\lambda_{\min} \geq 0$. Overall, the study demonstrates that transformer parasitics and frequency dependence have a substantial impact on high-frequency MMC stability and must be included in reliable HVDC interaction assessments

1.5 Impact of GFM control designs on system stabilizing effects

The works of the preceding sections identified cases where converters themselves can act as a source of instability. However, whether such converters also contribute to system-wide stabilization remains a question, and

Figure 1.6: Passivity properties of HVDC-MMC

even within GFM control, different design choices can lead to different system stability outcomes⁵.

The work in [5] investigates how the control design of a GFM MMC STATCOM affects both its own stable integration into weak grids and its stabilizing contribution to an interconnected wind farm system, challenging the common assumption that GFM converters are inherently robust against weak grid conditions. A key finding is that the voltage-feedforward (VFF) action in the current controller has opposite effects on weak-grid stability depending on the control structure: faster VFF improves the passivity and weak-grid robustness of GFL converters in the tens-of-hertz range, whereas it degrades the passivity of GFM converters in the hundreds-of-hertz range because of the additional interaction path introduced by the virtual-impedance loop. This distinction is rigorously demonstrated through passivity-sensitivity analysis.

The paper further reveals a potential contradiction between device-level passivation and system-level stabilization: indiscriminate passivation via high virtual impedance effectively prevents GFM STATCOM self-instability, but it increases the equivalent impedance seen by the GFL WTs, thereby worsening their weak-grid stability and degrading the GFM converter's

⁵This section summarizes the work published in: D. Lee, E. Avdiaj, F. J. C. Garcia, and J. Beerten, "Control design impacts of grid-forming statcoms for wind farm systems: Weak-grid integration and stabilizing effects," *IEEE Transactions on Power Systems*, pp. 1–13, 2026 [5].

Figure 1.7: C-HiLs experimental results using a detailed MMC, FD-cable models, and controller for MMC depending on control design strategy [5].

dynamic support, as quantified through the frequency-dependent power-flow Jacobian (FD-JB). To resolve this trade-off, a transient virtual resistance (TVR) strategy is proposed that adds high-pass-filtered damping to the virtual impedance loop, achieving passivity from the TVR cut-in frequency onward without substantially raising the low-to-mid-frequency impedance or sacrificing the voltage-source-behind-impedance behavior.

Controller-hardware-in-the-loop (C-HiL) experiment results are shown in Fig. 1.7. The experiment adopts a detailed system representation, such as a full-bridge MMC STATCOM, frequency-dependent cable models via an FPGA and a digital signal processor for the MMC STATCOM controller. This setup enables a more realistic validation of the control designs because it captures not only the detailed converter dynamics but also the cable frequency-dependent behavior and associated dynamic interaction, including delays. Therefore, they provide stronger evidence of the practical feasibility, robustness, and real-time implementation capability of the designed control strategy under conditions close to an actual system. The results of Fig. 1.7 shows that the TVR-based design maintains stability across all tested grid strengths down to $SCR = 1.2$, whereas both the fully passivated and non-passivated designs lead to system-level instability under the same conditions. A detailed 300 MVA offshore wind farm case study with multiple WT clusters further validates the generality of these findings.

1.6 Identification of AC/DC system supportive characteristics

Given that AC/DC coupling dynamics strongly influence stability and that system support capability is itself linked to system-wide stability, support capabilities and the underlying coupling dynamics should be examined jointly rather than independently⁶.

Our work in [6] introduces an extended AC/DC FD-JB framework to assess the system support capabilities of power converters in hybrid AC/DC grids, addressing the limitation that current grid-forming specifications and conventional FD-JB formulations focus almost exclusively on AC-side functionalities while neglecting the coupled AC/DC dynamics. The proposed framework extends the 2×2 AC FD-JB to a 3×3 matrix that captures the device's active and reactive power responses with respect to disturbances in AC voltage magnitude, AC voltage phase angle, and DC voltage magnitude, thereby providing power-system-friendly interpretations of converter behavior across both ports. A unified benchmark test system is proposed to evaluate the device under test through three layers: intrinsic system support capabilities, integration stability under non-ideal grid conditions, and system-wide stabilizing effects.

Comparative analysis of GFL and GFM control strategies, including droop-based outer loops and virtual synchronous machine implementations, reveals that GFM controls exhibit distinctly higher response magnitudes in the middle-frequency band for AC-side support, but adversely affect the DC-side response since they extract energy from the DC side to support the AC side, as confirmed by EMT validation showing significant DC-side power draw during AC support actions. Furthermore, droop gains are shown to influence not only the magnitude of the support but also the effective frequency band of the contribution, while internal energy controllers significantly modify the response with respect to DC-side perturbations through their use of DC current to manage MMC internal energy. Fig. 1.8 shows the results of identifications and validations of system-supportive characteristics for different control schemes. A DC weak-grid stabilizing test additionally demonstrates that higher DC-voltage droop gains maintain stability across all tested impedance conditions while lower gains lead to instability, with the FD-JB magnitude and phase information accurately predicting the contributing frequency region. Overall, the work shows that careful consideration of both AC and DC sides is essential when designing

⁶This section summarizes the work published in: D. Lee, E. Avdiaj, and J. Beerten, "Assessing system support capabilities for AC/DC grids with different control designs of power converters," IET AC/DC Europe, 2026 [6].

Figure 1.8: EMT validation results of J with respect to the disturbances $\Delta\theta_{s,ac} = 2^\circ$, $\Delta|V_{s,ac}| = 0.01p.u.$, and $\Delta V_{s,dc} = 0.01p.u.$ at 0.5, 1, and 1.5 sec, respectively [6].

supporting devices, and that the proposed framework provides a useful tool for enabling interoperable design of multi-vendor multi-terminal HVDC systems.

1.7 Interactions in HVDC links for offshore wind

Parallel GFM-MMCs are increasingly used in HVDC schemes as in Fig. 1.9a for offshore wind integration. Due to their multi-vendor nature and incorporation of novel controls, such as GFM, it is necessary to mitigate the risk of small-signal stability problems. Our work⁷ in [7] identifies and characterizes a previously unreported potential oscillatory instability in said systems; the issue occurs when both MMC operate in GFM mode in close electrical proximity, despite high synchronization-loop damping and the presence of a virtual impedance—realistic conditions different from previous works.

⁷This section summarizes the work in F. J. Cifuentes Garcia, et al., “Small-signal analysis of a bipolar grid-forming MMC-HVDC link for offshore wind integration,” in 2025 AEIT HVDC International Conference (AEIT HVDC), 2025, pp. 1–6 [7].

Figure 1.9: System under study and EMT simulation with S1 closed [7].

While long-duration EMT simulations might be needed to capture the phenomena via time-domain analyses, as shown in Fig. 1.9b, we leverage frequency-domain techniques to more efficiently reveal that the interaction manifests as a negatively damped anti-phase oscillation around 20 Hz between the GFM converters. The frequency domain analysis reveals that this interaction is independent of whether the HVDC system is operated in bipolar or parallel-monopolar configuration; conversely, the interaction disappears when the AC bus at the offshore MMCs is split (S1 open in Fig. 1.9a). Furthermore, the mode's damping can shift from negative (unstable) to positive (stable) depending on the active power flow as demonstrated by the results in Fig. 1.10. The selected modal impedance contains the relevant oscillatory mode around 20 Hz, which shifts from stable to unstable below 60% loading according to the phase-shift stability criterion [8].

Figure 1.10: Impact of active power flow in the unstable modal impedance.

These conclusions are validated by an EMT simulation in Fig. 1.11: growing oscillations 180° apart are present in the power of the individual MMCs, which damp out when the wind power production is increased above 60% at 5 s. Note that the total or sum power does not present said oscillations, and thus this mode is not observable from the common connection at the AC bus as predicted by the DC pole-dominant PFs in Fig. 1.10. These re-

sults also highlight that the operating-point dependency of interactions can be captured by linearization (frequency scan) at different scenarios.

Figure 1.11: EMT validation: operating point dependency of the instability.

Two control-based solutions are described and evaluated in [7] in order to mitigate the problem regardless of the operating point:

1. Active damping: a Transient Virtual Resistance (TVR) is implemented which restores stability by providing frequency-selective damping
2. Disabling the MMC total-energy control: this option can reduce the potentially destabilizing AC-DC dynamic couplings

Both approaches are validated through generalized Nyquist, closed-loop modal impedance analysis, and EMT simulations, demonstrating their effectiveness in suppressing the identified instability mechanism. Furthermore, it is shown in Fig. 1.12a that the active damping control results in a positive passivity index at the HVDC link offshore bus for the designed frequency region of the control. Moreover, the supplementary results in Fig. 1.12b demonstrate that the previously unstable closed-loop modal impedance in Fig. 1.10 is now stable and well-damped for all power flow conditions (the same y-axis scaling is used in both plots).

In addition, the consideration of additional control architectures is discussed as future work. Notably, the comparison between different MMC modulation strategies is particularly relevant since undesirable internal couplings have been identified under uncompensated modulation, which are negligible when compensated modulation is considered [9].

In conclusion, this work reveals a new potential interaction mechanism between parallel GFM-MMCs and demonstrate the practical effectiveness of frequency-domain analyses to its study and mitigation, which are key for the reliable deployment of offshore grid-forming HVDC systems.

Figure 1.12: Small-signal analysis results with active damping (TVR).

1.8 Active harmonic suppression in MMC-based HVDC systems

Once converter designs ensure stable operation, additional system-support functions can be considered. This section addresses the design and validation of active harmonic suppression control in MMC-HVDC systems⁸.

Our work in [10] addresses the challenge of designing active harmonic suppression (AHS) controllers for MMC-HVDC systems, where active filtering must be coordinated with existing MMC control functions and computational time delays can significantly affect stability. The work focuses on developing a systematic methodology to design and tune AHS controllers that suppress selected current harmonics while maintaining robust interaction with standard MMC control loops. Using dynamic phasor theory, the authors propose an LTI state-space modeling approach that enables small-signal stability assessment of MMCs equipped with AHS controllers, accounting for harmonic coupling, controller tuning strategies, and internal time delays. The results show that fast, bandwidth-oriented AHS tuning can introduce poorly damped modes, strong interactions with the output-current controller, and increased sensitivity to delays, whereas a “slow-tuned” AHS strategy yields effective harmonic mitigation with minimal impact on existing control dynamics. The impact of the AHS bandwidth on the modes of the system is depicted in Fig. 1.13, where $\omega_{\text{AHS},5}$ and $\omega_{\text{AHS},7}$ denote the bandwidth of the active harmonic suppression controller for the 5th and 7th harmonics, respectively. Time-domain simulations validate the analytical findings, and an additional case study demonstrates that similar interaction patterns arise in grid-forming MMCs.

⁸This section summarizes the work published in: Ö. C. Sakinci, J. Kircheis, and J. Beerten, “Active Filtering With MMC- HVdc Systems: Design and Small-Signal Stability Analysis,” IEEE Transactions on Power Delivery, vol. 40, no. 3, pp. 1706–1717, 2025 [10].

Figure 1.13: Impact of AHS bandwidth on the system's eigenvalues

1.9 Comparative study of model order reduction criteria

As converter-based systems grow larger and more complex, the analysis itself becomes increasingly challenging. This section examines which MOR approach best preserves the interaction patterns of interest while improving computational efficiency⁹.

Our work in [11] presents a comparative study of MOR criteria for interaction analysis in converter-dominated power systems, motivated by the observation that high-order state-space models, often arising from frequency-response fitting of black-box subsystems or detailed cable network representations, can make eigenvalue analysis and parametric sweeps computationally demanding and difficult to interpret. Time-domain criteria, including participation factor analysis and the infinite-horizon Gramian, and frequency-domain criteria, including impedance-based participation factors and the band-limited Gramian, are reviewed and evaluated on two benchmark systems: a single VSC integrated into a weak grid, and an MMC-based multi-terminal HVDC (MTDC) system with a cable network and a partial black-box subsystem. The single-VSC case shows that participation-factor-based reduction tends to produce aggressive truncation that fails to reproduce steady-state behavior, while the band-limited

⁹This section summarizes the work published in: D. Lee and J. Beerten, "Comparative studies of model order reduction criterion for interaction studies in converter-dominated power systems with cable network and partial black-box part," Cigre Paris Session, 2026 [11].

Figure 1.14: Root locus comparison of MTDC study case [11].

Gramian, when restricted to the sub-synchronous band of interest, better preserves both the transient response and the eigenvalue migration trends under PLL bandwidth sweeps, as illustrated by the root-locus comparison. This finding highlights that validating reduced-order models solely through time-domain response matching is insufficient: preserving eigenvalue trends under parametric variations is essential for stability-oriented interaction studies. For the MTDC case, a subsystem-wise band-limited sensitivity ranking is proposed to retain the most influential states separately within the black-box, cable, and white-box parts, and the resulting reduced-order model accurately reproduces the dominant transient behavior and the eigenvalue trajectories under DC-voltage droop sweeps, which are shown in Fig. 1.14. Overall, the work shows that the choice of MOR criterion strongly influences the conclusions of interaction studies, and that the proposed subsystem-wise, band-limited Gramian framework provides an effective and practically applicable approach for cable-dominated and partially unknown converter-based AC/DC systems.

Chapter 2

Large-Signal Analysis

This chapter presents the research within WP2 that analyzes the large-signal stability and transient performance in power systems with large converter penetration. As power-electronic converters progressively replace conventional synchronous generation, system stability under large disturbances becomes increasingly dependent on converter control strategies, their ability to support the system, and the dynamic interactions that emerge during these transient events.

The objective of this chapter is not to present a single analytical framework, but rather to provide an overview of several complementary studies that investigate different aspects of large-signal behaviour in modern power systems. While the individual sections focus on distinct applications and control architectures, they all aim to understand and improve system response following severe disturbances such as faults, generation outages, and large power imbalances.

2.1 Power system support capabilities: GFL vs GFM converters

The increasing displacement of synchronous generators by converter-interfaced renewable sources fundamentally alters power-system dynamics, reducing inertia and short-circuit strength and making transient stability increasingly dependent on the control behavior of VSCs. To address the lack of systematic comparisons between coexisting converter control strategies under large disturbances, our work¹ in [12] evaluates the transient support capabilities of three widely used VSC control modes—grid-supporting GFL, cur-

¹This section summarizes the work published in: W. Noots, F. J. Cifuentes Garcia, F. G. Puricelli, and J. Beerten, “Transient system support by VSCs: Grid-following vs grid-forming controls,” in ACDC Europe 2026, 2026, p. 7 [12].

Figure 2.2: Comparison between CC-GFM and VC-GFM controls for 50% GFM penetration in the system illustrated in Fig. 2.1 [12].

renewable sources, which leads to lower system inertia and larger frequency deviations following disturbances such as sudden loss of power plants or large loads ².

In [13], we focused on enhancing the power-support capability of GFM-MMCs within a bipolar HVDC link (Fig. 2.3), particularly in scenarios where steady-state power transfer constraints prevent the use of a constant droop control in the VSM swing equation. To address this limitation, we proposed an additional transient power term, implemented through a high-pass filter with bandwidth ω_{tr} multiplied by the transient coefficient K_{tr} , to provide dynamic frequency support without inducing unwanted steady-state power flow through the HVDC connection. This solution overcomes the challenge of achieving a large transient support and no steady-state contribution, enabling larger tunability of the virtual inertia behaviour. The time-domain

²This section summarizes the work published in: F. G. Puricelli and J. Beerten, “Enhancement of the power support from a bipolar HVDC link with grid-forming MMCs,” in 2025 Energy Conversion Congress & Expo Europe (ECCE Europe), 2025, pp. 1–6 [13].

Figure 2.3: Considered bipolar HVDC connection [13].

 (a) Impact of ω_{tr} , when $K_{tr} = 51.5$. (a) $p_{AC,1}$, (b) Frequency area A. (b) Impact of K_{tr} , when $\omega_{tr} = 0.1$ rad/s. (a) $p_{AC,1}$, (b) Frequency area A.

 Figure 2.4: Impact of HPF bandwidth ω_{tr} and transient coefficient K_{tr} on active power of MMCs $1p$ and $1n$ $p_{AC,1}$ and on frequency area A [13].

simulations in Figs. 2.4a and 2.4b demonstrate that the proposed approach substantially improves the Rate of Change of Frequency (RoCoF) and the frequency nadir of area A after a loss of generation at $t = 5$ s, while keeping the HVDC steady-state operation unchanged. Overall, the study in [13] shows that the introduced transient power term can effectively enhance the frequency stability of the affected AC area, especially when sufficient converter headroom is available.

2.3 Dual GFM for bidirectional support by HVDC connection

Given the system-support benefits of GFM control demonstrated in the preceding sections, a natural question is whether GFM can be applied to all terminals of an HVDC link. This section introduces the dynamic implica-

Figure 2.5: Time domain simulation results of the GFM HVDC test system with grid-frequency dynamics [14].

tions of such dual-GFM configurations³.

Our work in [14] investigates the dynamic performance challenges of applying GFM control to both terminals of a point-to-point HVDC system, where the conventional virtual synchronous machine (C-VSM) approach cannot simultaneously achieve fast DC voltage control and strong inertial response because its tracking bandwidth is inherently coupled to the virtual inertia constant. Although the two-degrees-of-freedom GFM (TD-GFM) method was previously proposed to decouple these objectives via a feed-forward path, its decoupling had only been clearly validated using a simplified analytical model that neglects detailed MMC dynamics, internal energy control, and the influence of the VSM damping coefficient. To bridge this gap, the paper conducts a systematic comparative analysis across three progressively complex scenarios—an active-power-controlling station, a DC-voltage-controlling station, and a complete Point-to-Point HVDC system with asynchronous grids and governor-based frequency dynamics. The results reveal that the simplified model produces overly optimistic predictions: as the inertia constant or tracking bandwidth increases, the detailed TD-VSM exhibits significant overshoots and degraded tracking performance, which is not captured by the simplified model, and C-VSM becomes unstable under DC voltage control with high inertia due to bandwidth conflicts between

³This section summarizes the work published in: D. Lee, E. Avdiaj, and J. Beerten, “Dynamic performance assessment of dual grid-forming control for high-voltage DC transmission system,” in 22nd IET International Conference on AC and DC Power Transmission (ACDC Global 2025), vol. 2025, 2025, pp. 27–32 [14].

the inner VSM loop and the outer DC voltage controller. Furthermore, the damping constant emerges as a critical parameter that substantially improves both reference tracking and inertial response across all cases, while the study of the full HVDC system with frequency dynamics demonstrates that inertial support provided to one AC grid propagates as a disturbance to the other, underscoring the need for careful parameter design and detailed modeling before deploying dual-GFM HVDC schemes.

2.4 Power coordination in bipolar MTDC system

Our work⁴ in [15] addresses the challenge of achieving reliable power sharing in bipolar MTDC grids employing MMCs, particularly during and after DC pole-to-ground contingencies. Traditional V/f, also known as asynchronous grid-forming control, although widely applied in isolated offshore systems, is shown to be unsuitable for parallel operation of multiple converters because it cannot regulate the active-power exchange, leading to unbalanced post-fault power flows. Existing solutions typically introduce grid-following control on one pole to achieve power re-balancing, but these approaches require control-mode switching and limit the benefits of fully grid-forming operation [15]. Our results show that the droop-based GFM control strategy in Fig. 2.6b is a simple and robust strategy offering inherent power coordination for bipolar MTDC systems. Through detailed EMT simulations of the three-terminal ± 525 kV bipolar grid shown in Fig. 2.6a, the study demonstrates that the droop-based GFM control restores equal power sharing between poles after fault recovery.

In addition, unbalanced operation is straightforward when required as the power references can be directly modified, as shown in Fig. 2.7 (right), thus overcoming the limitations associated with V/f control or mixed GFL and GFM approaches. Additionally, the EMT simulations with different inertia levels in Fig. 2.7 (left) quantify the impact of DC faults on the frequency of the larger synchronous area: fault detection, isolation and recovery are time critical, especially in low-inertia grids, to limit frequency deviations. Overall, this work shows that GFM controls with a droop term provide a technically effective and operationally simple solution for coordinated power sharing and post-fault recovery in bipolar MTDC networks.

⁴This section summarizes the publication F. J. Cifuentes Garcia, et al., “Power sharing coordinated control for grid-forming MMCs in bipolar HVDC multi-terminal networks,” in *CIGRE 2025 International Symposium*, 2025, p. 12.

Figure 2.6: System under study and synchronization/power control.

Figure 2.7: Frequency after DC fault (left) and unbalanced operation (right).

Conclusion

The work collected in this deliverable converges on a small number of cross-cutting messages about the stability and operation of multi-vendor, converter-rich AC/DC systems. First, grid-forming control is not a stand-alone guarantee of stability: depending on parameter tuning, electrical proximity, and operating point, GFM converters can themselves be the source of new sub-synchronous and harmonic interactions, both within a single HVDC link and between nearby links sharing a common AC bus. Second, these interactions are often invisible to AC-only analysis. The studies on AC/DC coupling, on the extended frequency-dependent power-flow Jacobian, and on offshore parallel-MMC schemes all show that the DC side, the converter internal energy, and the cross-port couplings can decisively change the stability picture. Third, a contradiction repeatedly surfaces between device-level passivation and system-level stabilization: measures that protect one converter in isolation can degrade the weak-grid behavior of the surrounding system, and only frequency-selective strategies such as the transient virtual resistance reconcile the two.

Methodologically, the deliverable confirms the value of combining small-signal analysis and large-signal validation. Eigenvalue, participation-factor, and admittance/passivity methods identify and explain the dominant phenomena and yield structural insight that cannot be obtained from time-domain simulation alone, while EMT and controller-hardware-in-the-loop experiments confirm operational relevance and quantify the impact of practical effects such as fault response, modulation saturation, and coordination via communication. Reduced-order modeling, when guided by band-limited sensitivity rather than purely time-domain matching, is shown to be a practical enabler of these analyses for cable-dominated and partially black-box systems.

For multi-vendor energy hubs, several operational and design implications follow. GFM control parameters, including virtual inertia, damping, droop gains, and virtual-impedance settings, should be coordinated across vendors rather than tuned in isolation, since similar dynamics tend to amplify rather than cancel each other. HVDC topology choices, including bipolar versus parallel-monopolar configurations and multi-terminal arrange-

ments, should be assessed jointly against small-signal interaction patterns and large-signal coordinated operation, since the same topology can be favorable for one and detrimental for the other.

Open questions remain on several fronts. Multi-vendor benchmark systems and shared interoperability test cases are needed to translate the present insights into reproducible specifications. Comparison of additional control architectures and coordination strategies, beyond those covered here, will further sharpen device- and system-level design rules. Finally, the integration of these findings into system-wide planning and protection studies, in coordination with other deliverables, remains an important next step.

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